

Academic Procrastination among Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students of Central Kashmir

Manzoor Ahmad Parray^{1*}, Dr. Precious Sheoron²

¹Research scholar, Department of Education, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi, Gobindgarh, Distt. Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab, India.

²Dean and Head, Department of Education, Desh Bhagat University, Mandi, Gobindgarh, Distt. Fatehgarh Sahib, Punjab, India.

*Corresponding Author: manzoorparrey12345@gmail.com

Abstract

The goal of the current study is to look at academic procrastination among male and female Senior Secondary School Students. Effects of different dimensions of Academic Procrastination were also explored. Kumar Reddy B.S. (2021), have found that gender significantly influences academic procrastination. For this study the sample of 383 Senior Secondary School Students were taken. The sample was further divided into 180 males and 203 females. The sample was taken from the senior secondary schools of central Kashmir. The range of their age was from 17 years to 20 years. Academic Procrastination scale by Kalia and Yadav (2015) was utilized for this study. This study aims to find the difference in academic procrastination and its dimensions of male and female senior secondary school students. The findings reveal that there is a notable distinction between males and females when it comes to academic procrastination. The findings also show notable differences among male and female senior secondary school students with respect to different dimensions of academic procrastination.

Introduction

Procrastination is the practice of delaying things that you view as essential or important in favour of anything else, usually something less urgent or significant. According to Silver (1974), "procrastination" is the act of completing a task after the optimal time has passed, where the term "optimal time" refers to the most suitable time to complete a task. Milgram and Toubiana (1991) defined procrastination in terms of four components, each of which is concise and vivid. It is first and foremost a postponement sequence. Second, it generates products that are below par.

Thirdly, it must be connected to a task that the procrastinator views as significant. Fourthly, procrastinating leads to a sense of frustration.

Procrastination is of various types, but the most important amongst them is academic procrastination. Procrastination that takes place in academic work or academic activity, such as writing a term paper, studying for exams, settings is known as academic procrastination. (Ackerman and Gross, 2005). Academic procrastination, according to Deniz et al. (2009), is the postponement of academic duties, such as preparing assignments and getting delayed for tests. Academic procrastination, according to Wolters (2003), is the act of delaying academic work despite the desire to do it on time.

Academic procrastination is caused by various factors such as Distraction, Lack of administrative abilities, Lack of personal passion, Laziness, Perfectionism, fear of failure, Internet, disobedience, self-confidence, metacognition etc. According to research (Reasinger and Brownlow, 1996), procrastination is caused by a variety of characteristics, including motivation, personality, perfectionism, and attribution style. Other reasons include 'being pressured by peers to do other things,' 'being overwhelmed by the tasks,' 'it takes too long to write a paper,' 'not being able to begin a work,' 'doesn't enjoy academic papers,' 'worried about not being able to meet personal expectations,' and 'worried about getting a lower grade or scores' (Kachgal et al, 2001).

It is assumed that pupils who are very motivated in their academics will not put off their study. According to research (Klassen et al, 2008), motivation is negatively associated to procrastination. According to Tuckman (1998), academic procrastination is caused by the lack of interest and motivation. Some students put off submitting homework and delaying learning because they feel unmotivated. According to Tuckman (1998), it is difficult to encourage procrastinators who put off work until the last minute. It is impossible to better their circumstances until modifications are made to increase their motivation.

The lack of self-regulation skills effects the time management. Procrastination will result from a lack of self-regulation abilities (Tuckman and Sexton, 1989; Senecal et al, 1995). Self-regulation abilities such as planning, self-evaluation, and self-motivation are essential for getting people to act (Ferrari et al, 1995). Some students may not organise their studies and assignments, while

others prepare their academic work but do not adhere to the timetable (Ferrari et al, 1995). These abilities are not natural, but may be acquired. They will be better able to stick to their routines if they are given explicit instructions (Milgram et al, 1992).

The adolescence is very crucial period in the growth and development of the individual. In this age young people suffer from mental, emotional and various behaviour problems, which are painful and costly to both the youngsters and to their family members. These problems severely disrupt a child's ability to function socially, academically and emotionally, and in the process also affect the person as well as his or her family, school, community and the larger society. One of the major problems which arise out of these changes in the adolescence is the academic procrastination. Various researchers have revealed that there is a significant difference in academic procrastination of male and female students. According to several studies, procrastination and gender do not significantly correlate (Johnson and Bloom, 1995; Ferrari, 2000; Watson, 2001; Klaseen and Kuzucu, 2009; Gafni and Geri, 2010). Rothblum et al. (1985) discovered that 32.4.6% of the male students and 57.4% of the female students were high procrastinators in their study. However, several contrary findings (Senecal et al., 1995; Ozer and Demir, 2009) indicate that men are more prone to procrastination than women. Instead of biological causes, there may be a mediator-variable, such as cultural or social climate (Ozer and Demir, 2009).

Objective of the study

1. To study about the difference in Academic Procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.

Hypothesis of the study

Ho1. There will be no significant difference in Academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.

Ha1. There will be significant difference in Academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.

Methodology

The current study included 383 students from government senior secondary institutions in Central Kashmir. A stratified randomization strategy was applied. There are three districts in central Kashmir: Budgam, Srinagar, and Ganderbal. Two Senior Secondary Schools were chosen from each District of Northern Kashmir. Each district's designated senior secondary schools included one for females and one for boys. The sample is distributed into two categories of male and female. Kalia and Yadav's (2015) Academic Procrastination Scale was used to assess the academic procrastination of senior secondary school students. The scale has 25 items divided into four dimensions: procrastination in homework, procrastination in exam preparation, procrastination in project work, and procrastination in extracurricular activities. The split-half approach was used to calculate the academic procrastination. The test-retest coefficient of 0.843 and the Gutman Split half coefficient of 0.713 demonstrate the scale's high reliability. The descriptive survey approach was employed in this study to determine the mean, standard deviation, t-test, and ANNOVA of the studied data.

Results and Discussions

Difference in Academic Procrastination of male and female Senior Secondary School Students

The fourth objective of the study was to analyze the difference in academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir. To achieve this objective, the academic procrastination scores of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. Means, Standard deviation and Summary of t-test have been presented in the table 4.4.1

Table 1

Difference in Academic Procrastination of Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Sig.
<i>Academic procrastination</i>	Male	180	76.8036	9.53171	6.338	.000
	Female	203	69.6233	12.02499		

The table 1 showed the mean difference between male and female senior secondary school students in their academic procrastination scores. The table shows that the mean score of male senior secondary school students was 76.531 and the mean score of female senior secondary school students was 69.623 and standard deviation of male students was 9.531 and that of female students was 12.024 respectively. The t-value was found to be 6.338 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was significant difference in academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. Therefore, the third hypothesis of the study which stated that “There will be no significant difference in Academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.” stands rejected, because there was a significant difference in the academic procrastination scores of male and female senior secondary school students and the third alternate hypothesis (Ha3) which stated that “There will be a significant difference in Academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.” stands accepted.

Further the difference in different dimensions of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students was studied. For these objective scores of different dimensions of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. The different dimensions of academic procrastination are as under:

1. Procrastination in homework (Dimension I)
2. Procrastination in preparation for examinations (Dimension II)
3. Procrastination in project work (Dimension III)
4. Procrastination in co-curricular activities (Dimension IV)

❖ **Difference in Dimension I of Academic Procrastination of male and female Senior Secondary School Students**

Further we studied the difference in Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir. For this, the scores of Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. Means, Standard deviation and Summary of t-test have been presented in the table 2

Table 2

Difference in Dimension I of Academic Procrastination of Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
<i>Dimension I</i>	male	180	31.7500	5.23662	6.182	0.001
	female	203	27.8698	6.68949		

The table 2 showed the mean difference between male and female senior secondary school students in the Dimension I of academic procrastination scores. The table shows that the mean score of male senior secondary school students was 31.750 and the mean of female senior secondary school students was 27.870 and standard deviation of male students was 5.237 and that of female students was 6.670 respectively. The t-value was found to be 6.182 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was significant difference in Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. So, this study revealed that male senior secondary school students procrastinate more than female senior secondary school students in case of Dimension I of academic Procrastination.

❖ Difference in Dimension II of Academic Procrastination of male and female Senior Secondary School Students

Further we studied the difference in Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir. For this, the scores of Dimension II of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. Means, Standard deviation and Summary of t-test have been presented in the table 3.

Table 3

Difference in Dimension II of Academic Procrastination of Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
<i>Dimension II</i>	Male	180	16.667	3.564	4.378	0.982
	Female	203	15.051	3.598		

The table 3 showed the mean difference between male and female senior secondary school students in the Dimension II of academic procrastination scores. The table shows that the mean score of male senior secondary school students was 16.667 and the mean of female senior secondary school students was 15.051 and standard deviation of male students was 3.564 and that of female students was 3.598 respectively. The t-value was found to be 4.378 which was not significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was an insignificant difference in Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. So, this study revealed that there is no difference in Dimension II of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students.

❖ **Difference in Dimension III of Academic Procrastination of male and female Senior Secondary School Students**

Further we studied the difference in Dimension I of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir. For this, the scores of Dimension II of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. Means, Standard deviation and Summary of t-test have been presented in the table 4

Table 4

Difference in Dimension III of Academic Procrastination of Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
Dimension III	Male	180	15.889	4.368	4.176	0.022
	Female	203	14.163	3.706		

The table 4 showed the mean difference between male and female senior secondary school students in the Dimension III of academic procrastination scores. The table shows that the mean score of male senior secondary school students was 15.889 and the mean of female senior secondary school students was 14.163 and standard deviation of male students was 4.368 and that of female students was 3.706 respectively. The t-value was found to be 4.176 which was

significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was significant difference in Dimension IV of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. So, this study revealed that male senior secondary school students procrastinate more than female senior secondary school students in case of Dimension III of academic Procrastination.

❖ **Difference in Dimension IV of Academic Procrastination of male and female Senior Secondary School Students**

Further we studied the difference in Dimension IV of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir. For this, the scores of Dimension II of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students of Central Kashmir were compared using t-test. Means, Standard deviation and Summary of t-test have been presented in the table 5

Table 5

Difference in Dimension IV of Academic Procrastination of Male and Female Senior Secondary School Students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
Dimension IV	Male	180	12.500	2.189	0.152	0.006
	Female	203	12.540	2.756		

The table 5 showed the mean difference between male and female senior secondary school students in the Dimension IV of academic procrastination scores. The table shows that the mean score of male senior secondary school students was 12.500 and the mean of female senior secondary school students was 12.540 and standard deviation of male students was 2.189 and that of female students was 2.756 respectively. The t-value was found to be 0.152 which was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was significant difference in Dimension IV of academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. So, this study revealed that female senior secondary school students procrastinate more than male senior secondary school students in case of Dimension IV of academic Procrastination.

Findings

From the study it was found that there was a significant difference in academic procrastination of male and female senior secondary school students. So, this study revealed that male senior secondary school students procrastinate more than female senior secondary school students. In case of Dimension IV of academic Procrastination female senior secondary school students procrastinate more than male senior secondary school students. But in case of other three dimensions male senior secondary school students procrastinate more than female senior secondary school students.

Discussions

The fourth objective of the study was to study the difference in academic procrastination among male and female senior secondary school students. Difference in different dimensions of academic procrastination among male and female senior secondary school students was also studied. It was found that male senior secondary school students show high level of academic procrastination than female senior secondary school students. Furthermore, it was found that procrastination in homework (Dimension I), procrastination in preparation for examination (Dimension II) and procrastination in project work (Dimension III) were high in male students than female students. Whereas it was found that procrastination in co-curricular activities (Dimension IV) was high in female students than male students. According to research by Kumar Reddy B.S. (2021), gender significantly influences academic procrastination. The reason for this is that boys are more often than girls exposed to society in the twenty-first century. Girls perform fewer roles than boys due to socialization regulations and family expectations. Boys may have experienced more stress and conflict than girls due to exposure, extracurricular activities, and experience. Boys, naturally, find a lot of things in their surroundings to be personally threatening. As a result, they struggle to organize their time effectively for academic tasks and put off doing their homework. The results are consistent with the prior findings of Wagner and Compas (1990); Jones (1993) and Grant and Cowpas (1995) who also indicated that gender has considerable influence on academic procrastination.

Boys in the Indian setting exhibit low levels of confidence, low levels of achievement motivation, high levels of aspiration, and low levels of frustration tolerance. In addition, guys

experience additional adjustment issues since they are unable to develop friendly relationships with faculty members. In Indian culture, boys are more likely than girls to hold important positions in the family, community, and institutions. His involvement in a variety of activities puts him in close contact with more people, which leads to more conflicts and problems. It is understandable that this would make it harder for him to focus on the coursework and academic activities at school or college, placing him on the academic stress.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declared no conflict of interests.

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